

“THE ONLY WAY IS UP”

LOCATION AND MOVEMENT IN PRODUCT PACKAGING AS PREDICTORS OF SENSORIAL IMPRESSIONS AND BRAND IDENTITY

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ABSTRACT

Based on embodiment research linking visual-spatial design parameters to symbolic meaning portrayal, this study investigates to what extent location of imagery on product packaging and visual devices portraying movement (i.e., an arrow indicating movement along an upward-headed or downward-headed trajectory) affect smell and weight impressions. To this end, participants watched, smelled and assessed product volume of a package for a fictitious brand of washing powder. Findings show that imagery located in the top-left (versus bottom-right) region of the package resulted in the perception of a light-weight (versus heavy-weight) package. Movement visuals connoting upward (versus downward) movement resulted in the experience of a less heavy-scented smell, but only in combination with imagery presented in the upper part of the package. In addition, brand identity impressions, package evaluations, and purchase intentions were assessed. With respect to these measures, location of imagery was most influential, with an upper location positively affecting consumer evaluations.

Keywords: product packaging, visual-spatial design, brand identity, sensorial impressions, embodiment

INTRODUCTION

In today's market, consumer products are often similar in terms of quality and functioning, and more than ever marketing communication strategies are needed to differentiate products from their competitors. Product and packaging design is a particularly

promising means as it can, amongst others, elicit aesthetic delight, attract consumer attention in cluttered store environments, and communicate symbolic product and brand qualities (Creusen and Schoormans, 2005; Hine, 1995; Schoormans and Robben, 1997; Van Rompay and Pruyn, 2011). Hence, when shopping for everyday products at the supermarket, consumers may base their purchase decisions on the product's visual appearance (Bloch, 1995; Crilly, Moultrie, and Clarkson, 2004), as when buying a 'special design edition' bottle of mineral water (aesthetic delight), an eye-catching chocolate bar (consumer attention) or a 'glamorous' shampoo bottle (symbolic meaning).

Consumers' reliance on visual appearances may also follow from a lack of relevant information (e.g., when buying a new brand of washing powder). Under these circumstances, product or packaging design may be a driver of consumer decision-making, because it allows consumers to draw inferences about brand positioning, product attributes, and (of particular importance to the current research) the product's sensorial qualities (e.g., smell, taste, or weight perceptions). In addition to shaping expectations, research indicates that people intuitively make connections between different sensory domains, a phenomenon referred to as 'cross-modal correspondence' (e.g., Schifferstein and Spence, 2008). For instance, Becker, Van Rompay, Schifferstein, and Galetzka (2011) recently showed that product shape may influence taste experiences, with an angular (as opposed to a rounded) yoghurt packaging inspiring a more intense taste sensation.

In addition to global product features such as shape and color, research also points at the importance of visual-spatial parameters such as (vertical) size and location of imagery in advertisements and product packaging (Deng and Kahn, 2009; Peracchio and Meyers-Levy, 2005; Schubert, 2005). For instance, Deng and Kahn (2009) showed that depending on whether product images are placed on the top or bottom, packages appear lighter (top) or heavier (bottom).

This research extends on these studies by assessing the impact that location of packaging imagery and visual devices portraying movement (i.e., arrows indicating movement along a trajectory) exert on subsequent (sensorial) product experiences. Specifically, and hitherto unexplored, we will look into effects of these elements on actual smell and weight sensations of a package for a fictitious brand of washing powder. In addition, we will zoom in on how location and movement visuals affect brand perception, and in particular the extent to which the brand comes across as *dynamic* or *active* (a key dimension of stimulus perception in general [Osgood, 1957], and product and brand experience in particular [Aaker, 1997; Geuens, Weijters, and De Wulf, 2009]).

The contributions of this research are threefold in so far (1) location and suggested movement have only received sparse attention in the consumer domain (cf. Deng and Kahn, 2009), (2) the relationship between these visual-spatial factors and cross-sensorial product experiences is unexplored, and (3) insights into how these design factors affect consumer impressions have not reached beyond overall evaluations, and as such provide only limited insights in how they may contribute to brand positioning. Before elaborating on the details of the study, first we will present a brief overview of relevant research.

LOCATION AND MOVEMENT IN THE PERCEPTION OF VISUAL DISPLAYS

The notion that location and the suggestion of movement are important predictors of visual perception is widespread among artists and researchers interested in the visual arts. Arnheim (1969), for instance, showed that artworks are

perceived as more or less *still* or *striving* dependent on the placement of their constitutive elements within the frame. Likewise interested in the symbolic meanings that basic elements of painting may carry dependent on their placement within a frame, Kandinsky (1926) argued that the above, and to a lesser extent the left, are expressive of *lightness* and *freedom*, whereas the below and the right rather express *heaviness* and *condensation*. In line with these speculations, research showed that people across cultures associate similar meanings with basic spatial orientations such as the 'above' and 'below' (Osgood, 1960), and more recently, Kandinsky's specific linking of symbolic meanings to specific regions in space has also been verified in the context of product packaging (Deng and Kahn, 2009).

The general line of reasoning accounting for such relationships holds that people entertain associations between location (i.e., 'top' versus 'bottom') and suggested movement (i.e., 'upwards' versus 'downwards') on the one hand, and specific affective qualities on the other (i.e., *lightness* versus *heaviness* connotations) because of our everyday embodied experiences (Dewey, 1934; Johnson, 1987; Lakoff and Johnson, 1999; Schubert, 2005; Van Rompay, Hekkert, Saakes, and Russo, 2005). For instance, discussing the dynamics of architectural shape, Arnheim (1977) argued that: 'the symbolic endowment of architectural shape is compelling only because the humble daily experience of climbing stairs reverberates with the connotations of overcoming the weight of gravity and rising victoriously towards the heights' (p. 210). In short, because we experience that going up takes effort, and all the more so with increasing load (e.g., climbing a mountain with heavy gear), we tend to associate heights with *lightness* or objects free from the forces of gravity, whereas the ground plane is readily associated with *heaviness* and people or objects that due to their weight are restricted to the horizontal dimension.

As such, this grounding of symbolic meanings in everyday embodied experiences explains why people associate locations in the upper regions of visual displays, or suggested movement towards these regions, with qualities that express *lightness* or *emancipation* (i.e., things of little weight more easily

'defeat' the forces of gravity). Recently, Deng and Kahn (2009) showed that these principles also apply to the perception of product packaging. Specifically, they showed that product packaging appears more or less weighty dependent on whether imagery is presented in 'light' (top, top-left) or 'heavy' (bottom, bottom-right) locations. Furthermore, they showed that the desirability of such locations varies with the type of product or positioning strategy, with light snacks, for instance, profiting from an overall perception of 'packaging lightness'.

So far, however, research has not addressed the intriguing possibility that meanings connoted through location and suggested movement may also impact actual sensorial product experiences. As hinted at, previous research already attested to the impact of packaging shape and color on taste experiences (Becker et al., 2011; Hine, 1995; Hoegg and Alba, 2007). However, it is an open question to what extent (arguably more subtle) meanings connoted through location and suggested movement may likewise impact sensorial impressions. In current research, impressions of product smell and weight are at the center of attention, and based on the foregoing it is hypothesized that:

H1a: Presentation of product imagery in the top (versus bottom) regions of a product package triggers perceptions of the product as less (versus more) heavy-scented and less (versus more) weighty.
H1b: Suggested movement upwards (versus downwards) triggers perceptions of the product as less (versus more) heavy-scented and less (versus more) weighty.

And taking into account the importance of these constructs to product and brand positioning strategies (Deng and Kahn, 2009), we will also study to what extent location and suggested movement foster related brand impressions. Specifically, we will zoom in on brand activity or dynamism as these constructs are arguably linked in consumers' minds to 'lightness' (i.e., objects of little weight are more flexible and dynamic compared to heavy objects that less easily change position). Hence:

H2a: Presentation of product imagery in the top (versus bottom) region of a product package makes a brand come across as more (versus less) active.
H2b: Suggested movement upwards (versus downwards) makes a brand come across as more (versus less) active.

Furthermore, research attests to the importance of congruence or unity among elements of product packaging because congruence leads to fluent or easy processing of the stimulus involved, and enforces the persuasiveness and credibility of the intended positioning (e.g., Hekkert, 2006; Reber, Schwarz, and Winkielman, 2004; Van Rompay & Pruyn, 2011). Based on these findings, it is expected that lightness (versus heaviness) perceptions are intensified when location and suggested movement match (e.g., a location in the upper region of the package coupled with an arrow suggesting movement upwards) rather than mismatch (e.g., a location in the upper region of the package coupled with an arrow suggesting movement downwards). Hence:

H3: Congruence of meanings connoted through location of imagery and movement visuals intensifies perceptions related to smell, weight, and brand (i.e., brand activity).

In addition to testing these specific hypotheses, we will also explore effects of location and movement (and their interactive effects) on more general consumer evaluations comprising packaging aesthetics and purchase intentions. Taking into consideration the associations of positive affect with 'highs' (e.g., 'I'm feeling up today') and negative affect with 'lows' (e.g., 'I'm so down'), overall positive effects of a 'top location' and visuals connoting movement upwards are tentatively proposed.

To test these predictions, product packaging variants were constructed varying systematically in terms of location of product imagery and suggested movement, and were subsequently presented to participants in order to record visual (i.e., visual perception of the package), olfactory (i.e., smell of its contents) and kinesthetic (i.e., perceived weight of the package) impressions.

METHOD

PRETEST

A pretest was conducted to ensure the effectiveness of the 'suggested movement' manipulation. To this end, sixteen participants (4 male, 12 female; mean age 26.4 years) rated three pairs of movement variants (one for each location condition; see Figure 1) on the item 'this image connotes movement'. Participants indicated (using 7-point rating scales ranging from "not at all" to "very much so") to what extent they considered this statement descriptive of the movement variants.

Comparison of means showed that the third pair (see Figure 1, panel 3) reached the highest scores (see Table 1) and thus most clearly connotes movement. Specifically, image 3a scored higher on suggested movement compared to image 1a ($F(1, 15) = 6.18, p < .05$) and image 2a ($F(1, 15) = 11.83, p < .001$). Similarly, Image 3b scored higher on suggested movement compared to image 1b ($F(1, 15) = 3.39, p = .08$) and image 2b ($F(1, 15) = 5.44, p < .05$).

Based on these results, the packaging variants for the main study were created. To this end, an existing package was redesigned with the selected movement variants (i.e., packaging fronts printed in full color). In line with previous research and common practice, these movement displays (i.e., packaging fronts comprising 'upward', 'downward', or 'no movement' [control variant] visuals) were either placed in the top-left or bottom-right part of the washing powder package resulting in a 2 (Location: 'top-left' versus 'bottom-right') X 3 (Movement: 'upward movement' versus 'downward movement' versus 'no movement') between subjects design.

In addition to the manipulations discussed, to enhance realism, all packaging variants featured a blue, cloudy sky, a slogan stressing product cleanliness and freshness, and additional product-specific logos. In order to assess weight perceptions, no indications of product weight were provided on the package (actual package weight: 711 grams).

Figure 1. Movement variants used in the pretest

	Suggested movement	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Image 1a	4.50	1.83
Image 1b	4.25	1.84
Image 2a	3.94	1.84
Image 2b	3.69	1.78
Image 3a	5.38	1.54
Image 3b	4.94	1.69

Table 1. Means and standard deviations for the movement variants used in the pretest

PARTICIPANTS

Participants were 144 students at a University Campus and shoppers of a supermarket (33 male, 111 female; mean age 31.0 years). All participants were naïve as to the purpose of the study and participated voluntarily.

PROCEDURE

Participants were approached individually and asked to participate in an evaluation trial for a new (fictitious) brand of washing powder. After exposure to one of the packaging variants, participants filled out a questionnaire assessing brand and packaging evaluation. Subsequently, participants were explicitly instructed to pick up the package, smell its contents and assess product weight. All packaging variants contained the same amount of an identical neutral-scented washing powder. After completion of the questionnaire participants were thanked for their cooperation.

MEASURES

The extent to which the brand comes across as active was measured with the items *dynamic*, *spirited*, *spontaneous* and *young* ($\alpha = .87$); items derived from Aaker's (1997) (conceptually related) *brand excitement* dimension, and Geuens et al.'s (2009) *brand activity* dimension. Participants had to indicate to what extent they considered these items descriptive of the brand. Responses were recorded on 7-point rating scales ranging from "not at all" to "very much so".

Participants' aesthetic impression of the package was measured with the items *appealing*, *attractive* and *beautiful* ($\alpha = .93$). Using 7-point rating scales, participants had to indicate to what extent they considered these items descriptive of the package.

To measure purchase intent, participants indicated (using 7-point rating scales) to what extent they agreed with the statements "I would consider buying this product", "I would recommend this product to friends", and "I would like to try out this product" ($\alpha = .86$).

To measure sensorial impressions (smell and product weight), participants indicated to what extent they considered the product 'heavy-scented' on a 7-point rating scale (ranging from 'not at all' to 'very much so'). Product weight impressions were recorded by having participants fill out the estimated number of kilograms.

RESULTS

Data were analyzed by performing a set of 2 (Location: 'top-left' versus 'bottom-right') X 3 (Movement: 'upward movement' versus 'no movement' versus 'downward movement') full factorial ANOVA's.

SMELL IMPRESSION

As for impressions of product smell, the main effect of 'Location' did not reach significance ($F < 1$, *ns*). The effect of 'Movement', however, was significant ($F(1,138) = 3.24$, $p < .05$). Pairwise comparisons indicated, as expected, that the product was experienced as significantly more heavy-scented in the 'downward movement' condition ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 1.35$) compared to the 'upward movement' ($M = 3.38$, $SD = 1.53$) and 'no movement' ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 1.47$) conditions (p 's $< .05$).

Furthermore, this effect was qualified by a significant 'Location' by 'Movement' interaction ($F(1,138) = 3.86$, $p < .05$; see Figure 2). Simple main effects analyses show that the three movement conditions do not differ in the 'bottom-right' ('Location') condition ($F(1,138) = 1.19$, $p = .31$), but that the difference between the movement variants is significant in the 'top-left' ('Location') condition ($F(1,138) = 5.94$, $p < .01$). Specifically, in the latter condition (Figure 2, right panel), the 'downward movement' variant triggers an impression of the product as more heavy-scented compared to the 'upward movement' variant ($M = 4.29$, $SD = 1.27$ versus $M = 2.88$, $SD = 1.26$, $p = .001$). The differences between the 'downward movement' and 'no movement' variant, and between the 'upward movement' and 'no movement' variant were not significant ($p = .07$ and $p = .12$ respectively). In other words, smell impressions triggered by the movement variants did only differ when imagery was placed in the top-left region of the product package.

Figure 2. Smell impression as a function of 'Location' and 'Movement'

WEIGHT PERCEPTION

As expected, the main effect of 'Location' on estimated package weight was significant ($F(1,137) = 8.73, p < .01$), indicating that participants considered the package heavier in the 'bottom-right' ($M = 853.77$ kilograms, $SD = 428.21$) compared to the 'top-left' ($M = 669.99$ kilograms, $SD = 303.88$) condition. The effect of 'Movement' and the 'Location' by 'Movement' interaction were not significant ($F_s < 1, ns$).

BRAND ACTIVITY

The main effect of 'Location' on brand activity was significant ($F(1, 138) = 4.00, p < .05$) indicating that participants considered the brand as more *active* when imagery was presented in the top left ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 1.38$) rather than the bottom-right ($M = 3.51$, $SD = 1.46$) region of the package. The main effect of 'Movement' was not significant ($F(1, 138) = 1.56, p = .21$), neither was the interaction between 'Location' and 'Movement' ($F < 1, ns$).

PACKAGE EVALUATION

The main effect of 'Location' on package evaluation was not significant ($F < 1, ns$), indicating that participants' aesthetic impressions of the package did not vary as a function of 'Location'. The main effect of 'Movement' was significant ($F(1,138) = 3.35, p < .05$). Pairwise comparisons showed that participants' ratings were higher when 'upward' ($M = 3.34, SD = .175$), compared to 'downward' ($M = 2.52, SD = .131, p = .03$) movement was connoted. The differences

between the 'upward movement' condition and the 'no movement' condition, and between the 'downward movement' condition and the 'no movement' conditions were not significant ($p = .47$ and $p = .74$ respectively).

PURCHASE INTENTION

Finally, the main effect of 'Location' on purchase intention was significant ($F(1,138) = 12.47, p < .01$) indicating that purchase intentions were higher when imagery was presented in the top-left ($M = 4.31, SD = 1.34$) rather than the bottom-right ($M = 3.47, SD = 1.47$) region of the package. The main effect of 'Movement' was not significant ($F(1,138) = 1.69, p = .19$), neither was the interaction between 'Location' and 'Movement' ($F(1,138) = 2.27, p = .11$).

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The findings presented partly confirm our predictions regarding effects of location and movement on sensorial impressions and product and brand evaluation. Extending on previous research (Deng and Kahn, 2009), our findings show that location of imagery impacts weight perceptions with imagery in the lower-right region of the package inspiring the sensation of a heavier package. In line with this effect, participants also considered the brand less *active*, which concurs with the embodied given that heavy objects are more *static* and less *flexible* (i.e., it takes more effort to change their position).

As for movement, however, our findings are less straightforward. First of all, no effects on perceptions of product weight were observed, perhaps suggesting that the manipulation was too subtle. That is, whereas the location manipulation involves an 'end-state' or 'destination' of imagery, the movement manipulation merely suggests an intended trajectory towards a specific destination. An alternative explanation holds that location of imagery is all-important with respect to weight perceptions (perhaps overshadowing effects of movement visuals) because heavy objects in particular are generally positioned on the ground. This may explain why imagery presented in the lower part of the package (corresponding to this experiential given) was so effective in triggering perceptions of a heavy package.

As for the movement manipulation, it was influential with respect to impressions of product smell. In line with hypotheses, upward movement triggered perceptions of the product as less heavy-scented (i.e., less concentrated) compared to downward movement. However, the interaction effect between location and movement showed that this effect only occurred when movement is presented in the upper (top-left) region of the package. Arguably, it is only in this condition (i.e., upward movement originating from the upper part of the package) that movement is perceived as extending beyond the confines of the package into the 'open space' above. As smells are commonly thought of as descending down on us from above, this might explain why an upward movement clearly transcending the vertical plane defined by the package has such a noteworthy impact. Also, this finding provides partial support for the prediction that congruence between location and movement boosts lightness perceptions. However, no congruence effects between movement and location were obtained with respect to the other measures, leaving open the question to what extent these design factors may interact in shaping consumer impressions.

In addition to the effects obtained on sensorial impressions and specific brand evaluations, of further interest are the effects of movement and location on participants' aesthetic impressions and purchase intentions respectively. In general, these findings concur with the notion that the vertical dimension and corresponding locations are generally associated with positive qualities or affective states (e.g., Schubert, 2005; Van Rompay et al., 2005) as also exemplified by linguistic phrases such as 'feeling high' or an 'elevated mood'. Lower positions, on the other hand, are generally linked to negative states or qualities (e.g., 'it's been downhill ever since'). However, in the consumer context, qualities such as heaviness and stability may also be central to product and brand positioning as for instance in the case of foods with high nutrition value. In other words, contextual factors such as product type and brand positioning should be the starting point when selecting locations and corresponding movements for product packaging (Deng and Kahn, 2011).

Of course, it is true that product packaging comprises many more design elements besides the dimensions discussed in this paper; factors that may likewise impact sensorial impressions (e.g., color and shape; Becker et al., 2011) and volume perceptions (e.g., container height; Raghubir and Krishna, 1999; Wansink and Van Ittersum, 2003). Taking into account the widespread (cultural) concern with dieting, low-calorie foods and corresponding light products, exploring such effects is certainly also interesting from a managerial point of view. However, care should be taken to ensure that the gap between expectations triggered by product packaging and subsequent sensorial impressions is not too large so as to backfire on product and brand evaluation. That is, expectations triggered by packaging may steer sensorial evaluations in a specific direction (e.g., a 'light' perfume bottle suggesting a *fresh* or *airy* scent), however when subsequent sensorial impressions diverge too much from initial expectations, consumers may readily discard the package as a driver of expectations or label the brand as *misleading* or *insincere*.

Finally, future research could also incorporate consumer characteristics such as design sensitivity (Bloch, Brunel, and Arnold, 2003) and consumer skepticism. Whereas the former involves, amongst others, consumers' sensitivity to (subtle) design elements (with effects of design elements on sensorial impressions arguably being more pronounced for design-sensitive consumers; Becker et al., 2011), the latter involves the extent to which consumers place faith in claims exemplified by marketing communications. With respect to advertising, skepticism has been shown to impact ad evaluations (e.g., Ford, Smith, and Swasy, 1990; Obermiller and Spangenberg, 1998), however skepticism has not been studied in the context of product packaging. Considering the growing importance of health or 'eco' concerns in society and corresponding growth of related claims and logos on product packaging, consumer weariness, skepticism and faith in truthfulness of packaging information may well be something to reckon with. Awaiting future research addressing these and related issues, in the meantime our findings attest to the feasibility of enhancing

specific sensorial product impressions through packaging design.

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